

Advancing Reproductive Biotechnologies for Endangered Species Conservation: A Multifaceted Approach

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ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: March 17, 2025

Accepted: March 28, 2025

Published: April 06, 2025

Abstract

Biodiversity loss due to habitat destruction, climate change, and human activities necessitates advanced conservation strategies. Reproductive biotechnologies, including artificial insemination, gamete cryopreservation, in vitro fertilization (IVF), embryo transfer, and somatic cell nuclear transfer (SCNT), offer solutions to genetic diversity loss and reproductive challenges in endangered species. Emerging techniques like inner cell mass (ICM) transfer and in vitro gametogenesis present new opportunities. This article examines the applications, limitations, and ethical considerations of these methods, emphasizing the need for species-specific optimization and multidisciplinary collaboration. Establishing genome resource banks and supportive policies is vital for long-term conservation. Continued research and global cooperation are essential to ensure the sustainable application of these

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Keywords: Artificial insemination (AI), Embryo transfer, Gamete cryopreservation, Reproductive biotechnologies

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